
ABSTRACT

**Machine Learning Techniques for Automated Wafer Health
Assessment using Wafer Test Data**

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Motivation

Main focus of modern manufacturing companies like the semiconductor industry is put on the automation of repetitive tasks. This coincides with the actual academic trend of using Machine Learning (ML) techniques for automatically gaining knowledge out of available data sources, using e.g. self-learning decision rules based on the underlying training data. In this paper we tackle the industrial need for quality monitoring of produced wafers via investigating wafermaps, using Machine Learning methods, to automatically detect critical patterns, which can be linked to production variability. Due to the high number of wafermaps, this investigation needs to be performed in an automated manner. A suitable solution is to design a decision support system, which notifies the expert in cases, when the calculated health factor of a wafer reaches a critical limit. The health factor is based on the presence of critical process patterns, detected in the set of wafermaps available per wafer.

Description

For the calculation of the wafer health factor, which indicates the presence and intensity of critical process patterns on the corresponding wafermaps, different data analysis techniques need to be applied in a smart consecutive way. First, each wafermap must be preprocessed w.r.t. outliers, missing values and noise to provide them with the characteristics of classical images. Afterwards, before the actual ML methods can be applied, useful features must be extracted. Based on these features, ML methods like clustering and classification algorithms are deployed for the purpose of pattern recognition. Finally, the health factor can be calculated, based on those detected and quantified patterns, which are assumed to originate from critical deviations during production. For each of these steps, various possible methods are available. The challenge is, to find the best combination of methods on a theoretical, as well as experimental basis, finally providing a reliable but also flexible procedure for the calculation of the wafer health factor. Hence, in this paper, we present a collection of adequate methods. Depending on individual assumptions and goals, these methods can be combined in the most appropriate way.

Innovation

Together with the ever increasing semiconductor data landscape, also the need for automation increases, because manual analysis becomes infeasible. In this work, we increase the degree of automation by providing an objective decision support system for

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assessing the health of a wafer by investigating analog instead of pass/fail wafermaps. This inhibits three major advantages: First, via automated detection of process relevant patterns, a comprehensive monitoring of each recorded wafermap is conducted, which would not be feasible with manual effort. Second, by investigating analog wafermaps instead of pass/fail wafermaps, the health factor acts as an early warning system for latent deviations during production. And third, the risk of error prone subjective judgements is eliminated, since the quantification of patterns is assessed based on statistical measures.

Results

As mentioned before in the context of defining a wafer health factor, various steps have to be taken to provide reliable results. For the preprocessing of wafermaps the following list states a number of potential methods, as well as their intentions:

- Outlier removal: This is important because outliers falsify the color space of wafermaps and disturb a clear pattern.
- Missing value replacement: For several image processing techniques, no missing values are allowed.
- Normalization: For comparison of wafermaps, consisting of different measurement units, normalization is needed to adjust the data scales.
- Transformation: Possible hidden patterns can be revealed by using methods like Independent Component Analysis.
- Noise removal: Wafermaps naturally suffer from measurement noise, which must be removed to eliminate this disturbing influence. For this task, Markov Random Fields can be applied.

Dependent on the expected patterns, features with different characteristics are extracted:

- Texture-based methods (e.g. Local Binary Patterns)
- Image segmentation methods
- Keypoint-based methods

Based on the extracted features, ML techniques can be applied:

- Clustering: Clustering can be performed to group similar patterns, solely based on the characteristics of the extracted features.
- Classification: This is a supervised ML technique, which requires labeled wafermaps. Then, e.g. a decision tree can be learned.
- Open Set Classification: This is similar to the classification but with the extension that not all possible patterns must be represented in the training set.

For the quantification of the pattern intensity, different statistical measures can be calculated:

- Spatial Entropy: The Entropy is a measure of uncertainty, whereas the Spatial Entropy additionally considers spatial information.
- Moran's I: This index is a measure for spatial autocorrelation based on feature locations and values.

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The execution of the individual steps and a selection of methods thereof lead to the final calculation of the wafer health factor.

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